
USAGE OF SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS TO PROMOTE WEB BASED LIBRARY SERVICES

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Abstract:

This Paper Discuss the Usage Of Social Media Platforms To Promote Web Based Library Services. Social media denotes the websites and applications that enable users to create and share content or to participate in social networking. In this digital era modern libraries use social media as a platform for knowledge sharing, information dissemination and communication. The present study examine using social media platforms to administer, distribute and disseminate information can greatly attract users and promote library usage in this information jet moving age. Library services can now be available to users on the go, anytime and anywhere, which have totally redefined Library services from the walls of the Library to the boundless spaces of the World Wide Web.

Keywords: WWW, Web Based Services, Library Services, Social Media Platforms.

Introduction:

The day by when the Internet is emerged, more specifically the World Wide Web which is one of its major services has completely revolutionized the way to communicate, studying, teaching, business, employment, education, healthcare and more. It has a major impact on the publishing and information delivery system in 21st century (Arora, 2001). Librarians can deliver various library services such as providing resources to support learning, cultural development and making available list of materials using social media platforms like blog, whatsapp, Twitter, Facebook, Youtube, Telegram and LinkedIn. These platforms through their unique features like blogging, commenting and affiliate

marketing, more participation, private messaging, discussion forums, media and multimedia uploading, interactive and collaborative learning increases active Library users, promotes Library activities and in turn generate unsolicited revenue for Librarians who actively manage these platforms. (Bakare, Umar (2018). Similarly in case of libraries too, applications of internet and web technologies have changed the way the libraries operate and provide information services to users. Libraries are playing a vital role for the promotion of education and research. With the application of this technology it became possible to have access to various information sources and databases available in various parts of the globe (Deka, 2007). It is not affecting only

the formats and resources of the information, but also how and where to provide library services (Bhatnagar, 2005). Traditionally, the library services were static. To access the library users needed to go to the library physically during the library opening hours only. But in web era, library services have become dynamic. Now a day the users can access the library at anytime from anywhere. No need to go to the libraries physically and no time restrictions. With the advent of information technology and web based services, contents are now available to users on their desktop. Digital Library Services, Internet Library Services, Electronic Library Services are the terms used interchangeably for Web Based Library Services.⁴

Social media applications, such as Facebook, YouTube, Quora, and Whats App, have become ubiquitous to the younger generation and provide new channels of socializing, entertaining, and information seeking. To keep pace with technology advancement, educators in formal learning contexts, especially in the higher education sector, have tapped into the potential of social media to enhance teaching effectiveness and to encourage active learning.⁹

As more libraries move towards providing services in a digital environment, the improved access to remote library collections is making the use of electronic information resources more realistic and more attractive. Traditional online services had transformed themselves into internet-based online services using web-based technologies.²

World Wide Web:

World Wide Web is one of the services of the internet. It is a way of

accessing integrated information in the form of web pages over the medium of internet with the help of web browsers. According to (Jeysankar, 2009) World Wide Web is a global network of internet servers which provides access to interlinked documents locally and remotely. It is a huge network of connected machine-readable text files hold on laptops throughout the planet which will give computer users' with data on a large sort of subjects. The information can be in the form of regular text, hypertext, pictures, sounds, use net news groups and other types of data. To access such information from web use client program is necessary like Internet explorer, fire fox, etc. Web uses http protocol language over the internet to transmit data. In the web each web page can hold not only information but also links to other pages. In each page a particular word or group of words are highlighted and there is a link between the highlighted item and other information, this is called hypertext.⁴

Web Based Services:

According to Madhusudhan and Nagabhushanam (2012) web-based library services means, "library services provided using internet as a medium and library website as a gateway with the help of web-based library automation software". Since the web-based library services are serving 24 hours service to the users, users can access to library services from their own computers without physically visiting the library.⁸

WEB is popularly used because the similar term of World Wide internet or net or online. The Internet and its "publishing arm" the WWW area unit necessary elements within the communication method. The web may be a consumer or server system accustomed accesses every

kind of data to anyone on Infobahn. The information is within the sort of regular text, hypertext, pictures, sounds, Usenet newsgroups and other types of data. To access this data, use a client program called browser. Within the web, the information is stored in pages. Each page will hold not solely data however links to different pages. In each page a particular word or sequence of words highlighted item and the other information related to that words in some other pages. This means that there is a link between the highlighted item and the other information, the service is called hypertext. When anyone wants to follow a link, the browser will find out where it is and connect the web server at that location, request the new page and 3 then display it on the screen. The WWW could represent AN intermediate type between recorded and unrecorded communication and knowledge transfer. Because it is a new medium we have not yet fully identified the dynamics of its behaviour. Keeping in mind today's tremendous increase in information and changing users' behaviour we can say that web is an ideal media for providing information. There are a unit some common facilities we will fancy type internet.⁴

A digital Library service manages and develops electronic services, the library websites and library staff. According to White (2001), it can be defined broadly as 'an information access service in which users ask questions via electronic means e.g., email or web forms'.¹¹

Library Services:

Library Services are defined as the facilities provided by a library for the use and dissemination of library material like books, journals, theses, dissertations, etc.

in order to meet the users' requirement. Some of commonly existing library services are cataloguing, classification, circulation services, reservation, renewal, new arrivals, current contents, current awareness service, selective dissemination of knowledge, reference service, document delivery service, interlibrary loan service, externally purchased database, CD-ROM databases, access to alternative library catalogues, access to on-line databases, internally revealed newsletters, reports and journals, bibliographies, indexing and abstracting services and so on. With the advent of internet and web the mode of providing such services has changed to web environment.⁴

Significance of the Study:

Web-based library services will become more widespread and sophisticated as the web becomes common place throughout the world, and to be successful players in the E-world. Libraries must continue to address the web design and implementation issues. As we actively transfer library services, our central purpose remain the same, to serve and teach users to find, evaluate, and use information effectively. The librarians should be expert to hold the hands of the users who are moving towards new communication paradigm a shift from face to face human contact to human machine interaction, from paper to electronic delivery, from text centered mode to multimedia and from physical presence to virtual presence. Despite these changes in communication technology, the reference interview will remain at the heart of the reference transaction. To meet these challenges the librarians may play a leadership role in providing better Web Based library Services facilities to their current techno savvy users.²

Review of Literature:

Bhatnagar (2005) the emergence of the World Wide Web (WWW) and Internet as a new media of information storage and delivery provide an unparalleled media for delivery of information with greater speed and economy. The web technology and Internet has changed the way of information is stored, retrieved and communicated in the libraries. As more libraries move towards providing their services in a digital environment, the improved access to remote library collections is making the use of electronic information resources more realistic and more attractive. Future and conclusion have also discussed in the last.²

Gavit, Keshav, (2019) with the emergence of the web and associated technologies, especially the planet Wide internet has opened up a wholly new medium for providing improved info services and resources for the users. Library services provided by mistreatment internet technology area unit referred as internet primarily based library services. The present paper mainly discusses that what are the web based library services, their features, advantages and disadvantages. Different web based services i.e. library webpage, Web OPAC, ask-a-librarian, email have been highlighted.⁴

Hadagali, Kenchakkanavar & Tadasad (2019) the paper presents how social media platforms can be used as effective tools to provide innovative library services in a university environment. The data was collected from both the central and state universities' websites especially to focus on the readiness of the university libraries. The outcome of the study reveals that the usage of social media in the university libraries in India is still in the formative

stage and needs to gear up to meet the growing expectations of the users.⁵

Kaushik (2016) social networking sites (SNS) are widely used by the library information science professionals for libraries for various purposes due to their characteristics, facilities and connectivity. This study provides views of library and information science professionals regarding usages of SNS tools and services for their libraries. Apart from this, maximum number of respondents said that SNS tools and services will be used for libraries in full extend in future.⁷

Madhusudhan & Nagabhushanam (2012) use of web-based library services by users in different sections of the university libraries in India and examines how some of the University libraries provide web access to their collections and user support for that access and the problems faced by users in accessing web-based library services. They will also learn how the unique web-based library services enhance the quality of web-based library services in Web 2.0 environment and suggests the new approaches for effective use of web-based library services.⁸

Manca & Ranieri, (2016) this study provides an updated critical review of the literature on Facebook as a technology-enhanced learning environment based on papers published between 2012 and 2015. It adopts a revised classification of the categories identified in a previous study, which emphasized three main Facebook affordances – mixing information and learning resources, hybridization of expertise and widening context of learning. Overall, the study found that Facebook pedagogical affordances are still partially implemented, although different types of educational use of Facebook exploit these affordances to different

degrees. It also provides indications for future research.⁹

White (2001) this analysis of academic digital reference services (DRS) in institutions offering undergraduate and master's degree education within the framework of diffusion of innovation theory focuses on the extent and rate of diffusion, the characteristics of libraries in each adopter category, and the re-invention of the innovation during implementation.¹¹

Zhou, Lee & Sin (2021) with the availability of a wide array of social media platforms, it is not surprising that students use social media to support their formal learning in a voluntary manner. To achieve effective learning, it is important for students to employ self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies to manage their learning process. There has been limited work concerning the SRL strategies that students use in a voluntary context of learning with social media.¹²

Objectives of the Study:

The present research has taken up the following objectives:

- To investigate social media platforms and web-based library services
- To identify the kind of social media platforms can be use to promote library services
- To Know the advantages of web-based library Services;
- To find out ways librarians uses of social media platforms to promote library services

Social Media Platforms:

1. Social Media Platforms and Library Services:

The social media platforms form the independent variables while the Library

services Librarian provides to their users are the dependent variable. The dependent variables are divided into library materials and librarian functions which are Books, Journals, Newspapers, Maps, Internet based, resources, CD/VCD and Lending services, Referral services, Reference services, Indexing, Abstracting, User education respectively. The independent variables are Blog, Facebook, Twitter and whatsapp.

2. Types of Social Media Used by Libraries

• Blog :

A blog also known as Weblog is an online journal style or informational website which displays information in the reverse sequential order, with latest posts or subject appearing first or at the topmost. Blog pages are social media web platforms where a writer or group of writers and readers or viewers shares their views on a subject or topic even news as it may apply. Blogging can be used to promote library services like library outreaching, dissemination of information, building library image, communicate both to internal and external users, and highlight new material arrival and promoting available materials in the library collection. Also Librarians can promote library services like opening hours, special library events, online discussion and community services like festivities in their local communities, ceremonies, sports.¹

• Facebook:

Facebook is a social media platform that facilitates social interactions between users. Facebook allows users to create group with unique identity where members can interact and share messages, pictures and even materials when they signed in. Librarians can use Facebook to promote Library service like hosting library homepage. Advertise opening and closing

hours, locations, website information, newly acquired materials and classmate interaction and discussion on special subjects. Facebook page can serve as a connect centre to Library users and librarians can also remind user through posting of up-to-date messages and pictures of the resources available in the library.¹

- **Twitter:**

Twitter is an online real time news and social networking platform where users post and interact with messages. The ease of posting, interacting and sharing of information on this platform has made it a very vital platform for librarians to reach and interact with library users. Information on the go with users responses can be tweeted at everybody convenience.¹

- **Really Simple Syndication (RSS):**

The Internet provides a wealth of information nowadays. Hence, the selective elimination of information has become the hurdle for the professionals out of this abundance of information. Really Simple Syndication (RSS) not only manages information but also reduces the information overload. The RSS, a new internet tool which allows the librarians to disseminate information on library news, current alerts and current arrivals of reading materials.⁵

- **Whats app:**

WhatsApp is an Instant Messaging service for smartphones or android based cell phones founded by Brian Acton and Jan Koum in the year 2009. It allows users to send text messages, images, videos, etc. to each other for free. The WhatsApp also allows to attach files viz. world, PDF, PPT etc.

The WhatsApp allows the users to stay updated on library events, enables the librarians to post news about the library,

images and videos of the library orientation programme and library events. It also allows librarians to interact with the users through discussion groups, image tagging, and receive comments and feedback and suggestions to improve the Library services. It allows the librarians to provide the most important services i.e. 'Ask a Librarian' without having to physically go the library.⁵

- **You Tube:**

YouTube, a popular web 2.0 tool which has been seen as a potential tool for delivering information literacy programmes to the users fraternity. Most of the libraries nowadays use You Tube for sharing videos on events, lectures, special talks, library tours etc.

You Tube helps the librarians to post videos on conferences, workshops, library events, library tour or bibliographic instruction for the benefit of users. User education / bibliographic instruction videos can be shown during the class hours on how to use a test, tool, database, search engine, formula etc. You Tube allows the librarians to save favourite subject related videos and also enables them to create a play list and share them among the users.⁵

- **LinkedIn:**

The LinkedIn Learning library allows learners to browse for learning paths, courses, videos, collections, and custom content. You can use the Learning library to find Learning content in an area of your choice, without searching for specific keywords. To access the Learning library. Resource utilization is the process of strategically measuring how effective resources are for those who use them. User can create a framework for assessing the quality of your resources to help you project their effectiveness and discover what library users need.⁵

- **Telegram:**

Telegram changed the mental and physical appearance of peoples' life style. These are very useful tools to communicate and share information among a mass of people. Libraries can also use these technologies to improve their services. Libraries can provide a wide array of services to interested users of these App. E-Journal and E-books (both text and audio) are accessible through these App. It provides location-based services, the internet/web-based OPAC on intranet. Library tours, instruction/orientation programs have been quite significant in bringing the non- users to libraries and also help the remotely located users. The Image Services in a library might offer a number of high quality, fee based photographic and document imaging services including digitized photographs, diagrams, maps, photos of places of national importance. It also provides the following services such as extension/inquiry, return information/inquiry, interlibrary loan requests, SDI service application, email service of academic journals, database use education application, etc.

3. Importance of social media and Web Based Services

Following are the Importance of social media

- It helps students, faculty and researchers to use library and its resources
- It helps library professionals to create, connect, converse, to contribute and share information to other libraries
- Process of exchanging knowledge and information will be more convenient
- It helps libraries to get closer to the users

- It helps libraries in building collaborative network with the users Location and time constraints in communication will overcome
- It helps library users in locating library resources
- It facilitates knowledge sharing
- It helps to feed user with information about new arrivals and events of the library

4. Advantages of Social Media and Web Based Services:

Following are the advantages of Web Based Services:

- It saves the precious time of the users.
- A large number of users can be helped simultaneously by using web based library services.
- Less dependent on the library staff for getting the required information.
- No need of library staff in large numbers to carry out library works and services
- Availableness of knowledge in several places and additionally in several formats.
- Fulfil information requirements instantly.
- Social media helps students in locating library resources
- Social media facilitates knowledge sharing
- Social media helps in promoting distance learning
- Social media allows user to create, connect, converse, to contribute, vote and share information
- Operating costs are minimal.
- Cannot be stolen or miss shelved.
- Saves considerable storage space.
- Immediate receipt of issue.

- Fast publication

Conclusion:

The first and foremost function of the library is to provide quality information service in order to satisfy their users with the right information at the right time. Web based library service is a trend. Although, we actively transfer library services but our central purpose remains the same, to serve and teach users to find, evaluate and use information effectively. Social media platforms enable the library professionals to create multimedia profiles with the goal of encouraging interaction between librarians and users. They provide a new platform for reaching users virtually without leaving the comfort of the websites they use the most.⁵

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